

Therapeutic potential of vardenafil in preventing sepsis-induced kidney injury: a preclinical study

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Abstract

Sepsis is caused by an infection-induced systemic inflammatory response that may lead to organ failure and death. This study aimed to evaluate the nephroprotective effect of vardenafil, a selective PDE-5 inhibitor, in preventing sepsis-induced kidney injury. Twenty-four male albino Swiss mice with induced kidney injury were divided into four groups of six animals. Histological and biomarker examinations were conducted to assess the outcomes. Vardenafil pretreatment significantly reduced creatinine, urea, and KIM-1 levels in CLP mice ($p < 0.01$). IL-6 and TNF- α levels in renal tissue were also significantly decreased by vardenafil treatment ($p < 0.01$), leading to a reduced inflammatory response. Vardenafil further inhibited BAX and caspase-3, lowered MDA, and increased antioxidant levels ($p < 0.01$). Nuclear expression of P-ERK1/2 was markedly reduced in the vardenafil-treated group ($p < 0.01$). These findings indicate that vardenafil protects the kidneys against CLP-induced sepsis by attenuating inflammation, inhibiting apoptosis, and exerting antioxidant effects. In addition, it has a nephroprotective impact by inhibiting nuclear P-ERK1/2 expression.

Keywords

nephroprotection, vardenafil, CLP, oxidative stress, inflammation, apoptosis, P-ERK1/2

Introduction

Sepsis is a profound inflammatory response to pathogens, frequently considered the main cause of morbidity and death among patients in emergency rooms worldwide (Rudd et al. 2020). The prevalence of sepsis, mortality, and its causes are on the rise, despite the progress made in technology and medicine. Although it is challenging to evaluate the global impact of sepsis, it was reported that each year there are around 48.9 million episodes of sepsis and 11 million fatalities worldwide associated with sepsis, which represents approximately 20% of all global fatalities (Abdelnaser

et al. 2023). Numerous organs can be adversely affected by sepsis, including the liver, brain, heart, kidneys, and lungs (Zhou et al. 2024). Acute kidney injury (AKI) is one of the most prevalent complications of sepsis, characterized by rapid renal dysfunction and elevated death rates, estimated to account for 2 million deaths worldwide each year (Peerapornratana et al. 2019; Alkhafaji and Janabi 2025a). Acute kidney injury arises in around 50% of patients with sepsis and accounts for over 70% of deaths among septic patients in intensive care units (Abdelnaser et al. 2025). While the exact etiology remains unclear, the widely accepted theory suggests that the immune response is initiated by diverse

endotoxins, proinflammatory cytokines, and mediators produced during monocyte activation in response to bacterial infection (Sato and Nasu 2015). The extent of sepsis-related injury is closely correlated with the intensity of the inflammatory response. When this response is prolonged or excessive, various inflammatory cytokines and mediators, especially reactive oxygen species, can lead to organ failure and death (Ghazi et al. 2019). The disturbance of the oxidant–antioxidant balance caused by an increase in oxidants is responsible for the initiation of these injuries (Alaasam and Janabi 2023). MDA is often used as an oxidant parameter, and GSH activity is used as an antioxidant parameter in studies. Furthermore, mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) represents a significant mechanism that induces an inflammatory response in AKI (Sun et al. 2017). Activated macrophages regulate these kinases, which phosphorylate subsequent genes and protein kinases, thereby intensifying the inflammatory response by augmenting the production of inflammatory cytokines (Li et al. 2023). Sildenafil may reduce sepsis-induced AKI via many routes. In a rat model of CLP-induced sepsis, sildenafil at 20 mg/kg dramatically lowered kidney inflammation scores and serum TNF- α levels, demonstrating its anti-inflammatory actions (Cadirci et al. 2011). Sildenafil also boosted glutathione (GSH) and lowered myeloperoxidase (MPO) and lipid peroxidase (LPO), reducing oxidative stress. Sildenafil and furosemide, especially in nanoparticle forms, improved kidney function indicators and histological architecture in a glycerol-induced acute renal failure model (Sabra et al. 2024). In a randomized controlled study of cardiac surgery patients, intravenous sildenafil did not substantially lower inflammatory parameters (Kumar et al. 2020). Extracellular signal-regulated kinase 1/2 (ERK1/2), an enzyme of the MAPK family, experiences rapid phosphorylation after renal injury (Masaki et al. 2004). Furthermore, the inflammation associated with sepsis triggers cellular apoptosis (Alkhafaji and Janabi 2025b). Reducing apoptosis is important to prevent the development of sepsis-associated acute kidney injury (S-AKI). Caspase-3 and BAX are considered mediators of apoptosis (Alkhafaji and Janabi 2025b). The CLP model of polymicrobial-induced sepsis is commonly employed to evaluate the possible protective effects of several drugs against sepsis due to its close similarity to human sepsis (Mohyeldin et al. 2023). Treatment of sepsis continues to pose a significant problem within the healthcare system, with patient fatality rates possibly exceeding 30–40%. Although there have been recent advancements in our understanding of the molecular causes of sepsis, almost all of these consequences remain resistant to treatment (Huang et al. 2020). Vardenafil, a potent and selective phosphodiesterase-5 enzyme (PDE-5) inhibitor, differs from sildenafil and tadalafil, reflecting differing pharmacological properties. It may enhance the glomerular filtration rate (GFR) by increasing nitric oxide (NO) levels and facilitating the synthesis and accumulation of cyclic guanosine monophosphate (cGMP) (Supuran et al. 2006). Phosphodiesterase-5 enzyme inhibitors are recognized for their ability to preserve tissues from oxidative stress by reducing the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) via the elevation of

cGMP levels; elevated cGMP levels result in enhanced nitric oxide (NO) bioavailability (Verit et al. 2010). It has shown protective properties in cystic fibrosis and experimentally induced hepatitis by alleviating oxidative stress and reducing nuclear factor kappa activation [22]. Vardenafil demonstrated improved histological markers and apoptotic effects in kidneys exposed to 24-h ischemia (Sousa et al. 2015). Studies indicate that PDE-5 inhibitors reduce inflammation in the serum and renal tissue of septic rats (Sousa et al. 2015). This research, for the first time, intended to examine the potential nephroprotective effect of vardenafil against CLP-induced sepsis-related acute kidney injury in male mice and the molecular mechanism underlying this effect.

Methods

Animal preparation

This experimental work used 24 adult male Swiss albino mice, aged 7 to 12 weeks and weighing between 22 and 35 grams, sourced from the animal center at the College of Science, Al-Kufa University. The mice were maintained in a regulated environment with a temperature of 22 ± 3 °C, humidity levels of 55–63%, and a 12-h light/dark cycle. The animals were individually housed in separate cages with available food and water.

Ethical considerations

Upon submission of the requisite petitions, the Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee (IACUC) at Kufa University authorized all experimental methods (permission number 2123 on 23 January 2025). All animal operations and experimental methods were conducted in accordance with the Ethical Principles in Animal Experimentation established by the committee.

Study design

After one week of preliminary adaptation, the block randomization method with an open-label design was used to divide 24 adult Swiss albino mice into four groups (six mice in each). The sham group underwent laparotomy under anesthesia without the induction of cecal ligation and puncture (CLP). The CLP group was subjected to the CLP procedure to provoke an AKI model. The CLP + DMSO group received a corresponding volume of DMSO as a single intraperitoneal injection 1 h before CLP surgery. The CLP + vardenafil group was administered a single intraperitoneal injection of vardenafil (10 mg/kg) based on a previous study (Sousa et al. 2015).

Experimental procedure

The cecal ligation and puncture (CLP) model was employed to induce sepsis. The mice underwent anesthesia with a combination of 100 mg/kg ketamine and 10 mg/kg

xylazine (Jabber et al. 2023). The abdominal wall of each mouse was cleansed and shaved using a 10% povidone-iodine solution, then a 1–1.5 cm midline incision was made. The cecum was exposed, ligated below the ileocecal valve, and subjected to a double puncture. It was then returned to its anatomical position, and the abdominal wall was sutured. Subsequently, the animals received a subcutaneous resuscitation dose of normal saline (20 mL/kg body weight) (Abd Uljaleel et al. 2023).

Preparation of the drug

According to the manufacturer's guidelines (MedChem Express), vardenafil is soluble in DMSO at a concentration of 100 mg/mL and should be freshly prepared just before administration. The dose was given intraperitoneally based on the body weight of the animals.

Sampling techniques

After 24 h following the CLP procedure, the animals were euthanized, and blood and tissue samples were collected as described below:

Blood sample collection

Blood was collected by the direct cardiac puncture method following euthanasia. The blood was drawn into a gel tube and centrifuged at 6000 rpm for 10 minutes to extract the serum. Serum urea and creatinine levels were evaluated using a spectrophotometric technique at an absorbance wavelength of 550 nm. Serum KIM-1 levels were quantified using commercially available ELISA kits (Alaasam et al. 2024).

Biochemical examination for tissue specimens

A kidney specimen was obtained, rinsed with normal saline to eliminate any blood or clots, and bisected into two halves post-experimentation. One half was homogenized using a high-performance ultrasonic liquid processor in a 1:10 (w/v) phosphate-buffered saline mixture containing 1% Triton X-100 and a protease inhibitor cocktail. The homogenate was centrifuged for 10 minutes at 5000 rpm at 4 °C (Alaasam et al. 2024). The supernatant was collected for the quantification of IL-6, TNF- α , MDA, GSH, BAX, and caspase-3 using available ELISA kits. The other renal portion was used to measure phospho-ERK 1/2 (P-ERK 1/2) levels by immunohistochemistry and to examine renal tissue histopathology.

Histopathological specimen collection

After sacrificing the mice, kidney tissues were collected and rinsed with normal saline solution to eliminate any blood or clots. After fixation in 10% formalin, dehydration in graded alcohols, clearing with xylene, and embedding in paraffin, the samples were processed into blocks. These

blocks were cut to a thickness of 5 microns. A histopathologist examined hematoxylin-eosin-stained tissue slices (Alaasam and Janabi 2023). Histopathological assessment focused on identifying features including cellular hypertrophy, cytoplasmic eosinophilia, tubular dilation, loss of brush border integrity, formation of protein casts, desquamation of epithelial cells into the lumen, inflammatory responses, cellular lysis, and necrosis. The sections were examined using light microscopy at magnifications of $\times 100$ or $\times 400$. Histopathological changes were assessed based on the proportion of compromised kidney tubules. Tissue injury was scored on a scale from 0 to 4, where 0 indicates no damage; 1: less than 25%; 2: 25–50%; 3: 50–75%; and 4: more than 75% (Hassoon et al. 2019).

Tissue sampling for the immunohistochemistry technique

An immunohistochemical examination was performed to assess phospho-ERK 1/2 expression in renal tissue. Tissue slices were first deparaffinized with xylene and then rehydrated using graded alcohol solutions. Antigen retrieval was achieved by heating the samples for 20 minutes. Endogenous peroxidase activity was inhibited with 3% hydrogen peroxide for 5 minutes. After rinsing with washing buffer, the sections were incubated for 30 minutes with a phospho-ERK 1/2 polyclonal antibody (Elabscience) diluted at 1:100, followed by an additional wash. Subsequently, horseradish peroxidase-conjugated secondary antibodies were applied for 30 minutes. The sections were then exposed to freshly prepared DAB for 10 minutes. The tissues were counterstained with hematoxylin and prepared for microscopic analysis (Abbas et al. 2021). The expression of phospho-ERK 1/2 was evaluated using the H-score method, which ranges from 0 to 300. The score was calculated by multiplying the staining intensity by the percentage of positively stained cells. Staining intensity was scored from 0 to 3, where 0 indicates no staining, 1 indicates faint staining, 2 indicates moderate staining, and 3 indicates strong staining. The percentage of positively stained cells ranged from 0% to 100% (Abbas et al. 2021).

Biochemical assessment of kidney function and injury markers

Serum concentrations of both creatinine and urea were measured using the spectrophotometric method, while the serum level of kidney injury molecule-1 (KIM-1) was evaluated using a commercially available ELISA kit from Bioassay Technology Laboratory, China (Cat. No. E0617Mo), following the manufacturer's guidelines.

Analysis of TNF- α and IL-6

Levels of TNF- α and IL-6 were quantified using ELISA kits for TNF- α (Cat. No. E0117Mo) and IL-6 (Cat. No. E0049Mo) from Bioassay Technology Laboratory, China, in accordance with the manufacturer's instructions.

Assessment of GSH and MDA

The levels of GSH and MDA were measured using ELISA kits for GSH (Cat. No. SL0476Mo) and MDA (Cat. No. SL0370Mo) from SunLong Biotech Co., Ltd., China, following the manufacturer's instructions.

Assessment of caspase-3 and BAX

The levels of caspase-3 and BAX were quantified using the caspase-3 ELISA kit (Cat. No. E1513Mo) from Bioassay Technology Laboratory, China, and the BAX ELISA kit (Cat. No. SL0766Mo) from SunLong Biotech Co., Ltd., China, according to the manufacturers' guidelines.

Assessment of phospho-ERK 1/2

The expression of phospho-ERK 1/2 was assessed by immunohistochemistry. The primary antibody, phospho-ERK 1/2 (Tyr204) polyclonal antibody, was obtained from Elabscience, China. The secondary antibody, Mouse/Rabbit PolyDetector Plus DAB HRP Brown, was obtained from BIO SB, USA.

Statistical analysis

The statistical analyses were conducted using GraphPad Prism version 10.1.0. Data were expressed as mean \pm standard error of the mean. Multiple group comparisons were performed using one-way ANOVA followed by the Bonferroni post hoc test. The Kruskal-Wallis nonparametric test was additionally used to evaluate histological differences across the study groups. A p-value less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Sepsis was induced using the CLP model. One hour before CLP, the animals were administered DMSO or vardenafil (10 mg/kg) or left untreated. Multiple biochemical and histological parameters were examined after 24 h of sepsis induction to evaluate the severity of renal injury.

Effect on renal function and renal injury parameters

Serum levels of urea, creatinine, and KIM-1 were significantly higher in the CLP and CLP + DMSO groups than in the sham group. However, no substantial differences were observed between the CLP and CLP + DMSO groups. In contrast, mice treated with vardenafil exhibited a significant reduction in these serum markers compared to the CLP group (Fig. 1). These findings suggest that vardenafil may enhance renal function in mice with sepsis-induced acute kidney injury.

Effect on inflammatory parameters

The concentrations of inflammatory cytokines IL-6 and TNF- α were markedly elevated in the renal tissues of mice in the CLP and CLP + DMSO groups compared to the sham group (Fig. 2). There were no significant differences between the CLP and CLP + DMSO groups. However, the vardenafil-treated group showed a significant reduction in IL-6 and TNF- α levels in renal tissue compared to the CLP group. These results indicate that vardenafil mitigated inflammation in the kidneys of mice affected by sepsis-induced AKI.

Effect on oxidative stress

The renal tissue level of MDA was significantly increased, whereas GSH levels were markedly decreased in the CLP and CLP + DMSO groups compared to the sham group. The CLP and CLP + DMSO groups exhibited no significant difference. Vardenafil pretreatment significantly reduced the renal tissue level of MDA and increased renal GSH levels when compared with those of the CLP and CLP + DMSO groups (Fig. 3).

Effect on apoptotic markers

The renal tissue levels of apoptotic markers, including caspase-3 and Bax, were significantly elevated in the CLP and CLP + DMSO groups in comparison to the sham group. The difference between the CLP and CLP + DMSO groups was not significant. Vardenafil treatment exhibited an antiapoptotic effect, as indicated by the marked decrease in Bax and caspase-3 levels compared with the CLP group (Fig. 3). These findings indicate that vardenafil exerted antiapoptotic effects in the kidneys of mice with sepsis-induced AKI.

Effect on phospho-ERK 1/2

Immunohistochemistry findings (Fig. 4) revealed a markedly elevated nuclear expression of p-ERK1/2 in both the CLP and CLP + DMSO groups relative to the sham group, with no significant difference observed between the CLP and CLP + DMSO groups. Nonetheless, pretreatment with vardenafil significantly reduced p-ERK1/2 protein expression compared to the CLP and CLP + DMSO groups (Figs 4, 5).

Histopathological finding

Microscopic examination of kidney tissues from the CLP and CLP + DMSO groups revealed notable pathological alterations, including tubular cell swelling, brush border loss, vascular congestion, cytoplasmic eosinophilia and vacuolization, inflammation, and cast formation. In contrast, the sham group exhibited normal renal architecture. Vardenafil pretreatment preserved renal tissue structure, with only mild tubular swelling, reduced vascular congestion, and minimal brush border loss. The histopathologi-

Figure 1. Renal function analysis. 24 h after the CLP procedure. **A.** Serum urea level; **B.** Serum creatinine level, and **C:** Serum KIM1 level. One-way ANOVA with the Bonferroni test was performed. Data are expressed as mean \pm SEM, with $n = 6$ mice per group, ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$, **** $P < 0.0001$.

cal score for the vardenafil-treated group was significantly lower than that of the CLP and vehicle groups, as shown in Figs 6, 7, Table 1.

Discussion

Sepsis is characterized by organ dysfunction resulting from an abnormal or dysregulated immune response. Although multiple organs can be affected, the kidney is one of the primary organs susceptible to inflammation

Table 1. Differences in the histopathological score in the four experimental groups.

Score	sham		CLP		CLP + DMSO		CLP + Vardenafil	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Normal (0)	5	83.33%	0	0%	0	0%	3	50%
Mild (1)	1	16.67%	0	0%	0	0%	2	33.33%
Moderate (2)	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	1	16.67%
Severe (3)	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%
Highly severe (4)	0	0%	6	100%	6	100%	0	0%
Total	6	100%	6	100%	6	100%	6	100%

Figure 2. Analysis of renal inflammatory markers. 24 h after the CLP procedure. **A.** TNF- α level; **B.** IL-6 level. The data were analyzed using one-way ANOVA and the Bonferroni test, with results presented as mean \pm SEM (n = 6 mice/group); **P < 0.01, ***P < 0.001, ****P < 0.0001.

Figure 3. Analysis of renal oxidative stress and apoptotic indicators. 24 h after the CLP procedure. **A.** MDA level; **B.** GSH level; **C.** Caspase-3 level; **D.** BAX level. One-way ANOVA was conducted, followed by the Bonferroni test for analysis. Results are presented as mean \pm SEM, n = 6 mice per group, with significance indicated as ***P < 0.001 and ****P < 0.0001.

Figure 4. Photomicrographs of the renal section. **A.** Sham group shows a negative nuclear p-ERK 1/2 expression. IHC, X400; **B.** CLP group positive nuclear p-ERK 1/2 expression in 20% of examined cells (black arrows); IHC, X400; **C.** CLP + DMSO group positive nuclear p-ERK 1/2 expression in 15% of examined cells (black arrows). IHC, X400, and **D.** CLP + vardenafil-treated group showing positive nuclear p-ERK 1/2 expression in 1% of examined cells (black arrows), IHC, X400.

and damage during sepsis (Caraballo and Jaimes 2019). The current study is the first to investigate the possible nephroprotective impact of vardenafil on S-AKI. The CLP method has been shown to cause sepsis, further renal impairment, and AKI (Jabber et al. 2023). This study examined the antioxidant, anti-inflammatory,

anti-apoptotic, renal function, and renal injury effects of vardenafil in kidney damage caused by endotoxemia induced by the CLP model in mice. This experimental study indicated a substantial increase in serum urea, creatinine, and KIM-1 in both CLP and CLP + DMSO groups in comparison with the sham group. The findings

Figure 5. The mean H-score of nuclear p-ERK1/2 expression in renal tissue was measured in the 4 experimental groups 24 h after CLP. Data were analyzed using one-way ANOVA and the Bonferroni test. Results are presented as mean \pm SEM, with $n = 6$ mice per group. Statistical significance is indicated as $**P < 0.01$ and $****P < 0.0001$.

we obtained are consistent with those of Wang et al., who documented elevated blood concentrations of urea, creatinine, and KIM-1 in mice with sepsis produced by the CLP model (Wang et al. 2018). KIM-1 is a sensitive marker for tubular injury, rarely detected in normal kidney tissue but rapidly observed in serum during acute renal tubular damage (Q Jallawee and Janabi 2024). This study's findings indicated a significant decrease in blood levels of urea, creatinine, and KIM-1 in the vardenafil-treated group relative to the CLP and CLP + DMSO groups. These markers serve as significant indicators of renal function and often increase after renal damage. However, there was a significant decrease in septic mice pretreated with vardenafil, indicating that vardenafil enhanced renal function and mitigated renal damage. A previous investigation reported similar results with vardenafil (Zisis et al. 2022). The development of severe sepsis is significantly characterized by an increase in the expression of inflammatory mediators, particularly TNF- α and IL-6 (Inandiklioglu et al. 2021). The TNF- α and IL-6 levels in renal tissue were significantly elevated in the CLP and CLP + DMSO groups in comparison to the sham group in this study. Our findings are consistent with previously published data (Hamza et al. 2022). Administration of vardenafil prior to the CLP process significantly decreased IL-6 and TNF- α levels in kidney tissues. This aligns with the results of Benli et al., which indicated that PDE-5 inhibitors diminish inflammatory markers in sepsis (Benli et al. 2017). Oxidative stress was also crucial in renal sepsis. Renal tissue damage results from the production of free radicals that oxidize membrane lipids, causing oxidative damage to proteins

and DNA, eventually leading to apoptosis and cellular death (Fawzy et al. 2022). Therefore, the oxidative stress marker MDA, as well as the antioxidant marker GSH, were assessed in kidney homogenates. In this study, the presence of elevated MDA levels in renal tissues of CLP and CLP + DMSO groups is indicative of oxidative damage to the kidney, a crucial element in the pathophysiology of renal injury during sepsis. Additionally, in comparison to the sham group, these groups exhibited a substantial decrease in GSH levels. Our findings indicated that the administration of vardenafil resulted in a substantial reduction in MDA levels and a notable increase in the antioxidant GSH levels, thereby reducing oxidative damage and lipid peroxidation. This finding indicates that vardenafil may offer protective effects against oxidative stress in kidney injury caused by sepsis. The reduced MDA levels and sustained GSH levels indicate that vardenafil may mitigate DNA damage induced by ROS generation. Apoptosis significantly contributes to organ damage in sepsis, particularly in renal damage. The main mechanism driving apoptosis in renal tubular cells involves the initiation of caspase-3 and BAX, along with the inhibition of anti-apoptotic Bcl-2 (Alsaaty and Janabi 2024). Caspase-3 and BAX activation are hallmarks of apoptotic cell death, and evaluating their activity offers information regarding the degree of apoptosis within tissues (Tan et al. 2023). In our study, the apoptosis markers caspase-3 and BAX increased significantly in the renal tissue of the CLP + DMSO groups compared to the sham group, suggesting significant apoptosis in these mice. In contrast, the vardenafil-pretreated group had decreased caspase-3 and BAX levels compared to the CLP group, suggesting its potential to diminish apoptosis in renal tissue after sepsis. This reduction in caspase-3 and BAX activity, consistent with previous studies (Sousa et al. 2015), indicates that vardenafil may have anti-apoptotic characteristics, thereby enhancing its protective benefits against renal damage in sepsis. Vardenafil may protect the structural and functional integrity of renal cells during sepsis by decreasing caspase-3 and BAX activity. The MAPK signaling pathway is crucial for regulating inflammation and immunological responses. MAPKs, a highly conserved signaling cascade found in virtually all eukaryotic cells, modulate the activity of target proteins via phosphorylation, thereby participating in several processes within cells, including cell proliferation, development, division, and function (Lu et al. 2020). ERK 1/2 signaling is associated with inflammation and cellular apoptosis in acute kidney injury (Gong et al. 2022). Phosphorylation of ERK 1/2 acts as a primary initiator of inflammation and renal cell damage in sepsis-induced acute kidney injury (AKI). In our study, increased P-ERK1/2 expression was observed in renal tissue of the CLP and vehicle groups in contrast to the sham group. An increase in P-ERK1/2 due to sepsis was also reported by a similar research study (Liang et al. 2024). Vardenafil exerts nephroprotection by reducing

Figure 6. Hematoxylin and eosin staining of renal tissues. **A.** Sham group: Kidney cross-section showing normal histological structure. Magnification: 400×; **B.** Control (CLP) group: with a score of 4, damage involving 95% of renal tubules, cellular swelling and increased cytoplasmic eosinophilia (red arrows), and vascular congestion and hemorrhage (orange arrow), Magnification: 400×; **C.** DMSO group: with a score of 4, damage involving 95% of renal tubules, damaged tubules (red arrow), damaged tubules (red arrow). Magnification: 400×; **D.** Vardenafil-treated group, with a score of 2, damage involving 30% of the renal tubules, a normal tubule (green arrow), and damaged tubules (red arrow). Magnification: 400×.

P-ERK1/2 expression in kidney tissue. This differs from prior research in ischemia-reperfusion models, where vardenafil was linked to enhanced ERK1/2 phosphorylation, indicating a protective mechanism via ERK activation (Kyriazis et al. 2013). The differing outcomes may be due to the distinct pathophysiological pathways: while ERK activation may enhance cell survival and repair in ischemic injury, its excessive activation in sepsis

can worsen inflammatory responses and renal impairment. Inhibition of ERK 1/2 phosphorylation in sepsis reduces the severity of kidney damage by decreasing the inflammatory and oxidative stress mediators (Shi et al. 2024). Bax and caspase-3 are essential downstream effectors for the ERK pathway (Fu et al. 2020). In addition to the findings, there are various limitations to this study. First, only one dose of vardenafil was tested,

Figure 7. The histopathological damage score was evaluated in the 4 experimental groups 24 h after CLP. Mice were pre-treated one hour before CLP with either DMSO, vardenafil (10 mg/kg), or untreated (sham and CLP groups). The non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis one-way ANOVA was used for data analysis. Results are presented as mean \pm SEM, with $n = 6$ mice per group. Statistical significance is indicated as * $P < 0.05$ and ** $P < 0.01$.

restricting the understanding of the dose-response relationship and the effects of delayed administration. Further studies are needed. Another limitation is that the endpoint assessed at 24 h post-CLP offers insights into early renal changes but does not address long-term outcomes such as survival or the progression of chronic kidney injury.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that vardenafil treatment can mitigate sepsis-induced renal injury by diminishing ERK1/2 phosphorylation, reducing oxidative stress, inhibiting apoptosis, and attenuating inflammatory mediators.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

Experiments on animals: Upon submission of the requisite petitions, the Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee (IA-CUC) at Kufa University authorized all experimental methods (permission number 2123 on 23/1/2025). All animal operations and experimental methods were conducted in accordance with the Ethical Principles in Animal Experimentation established by the committee.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

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Author contributions

All authors contributed equally to this article. G.M.A. was responsible for data collection, statistical analysis, and drafting the manuscript. A.M.J. contributed to the main idea, study design, and critical revision of the manuscript.

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Data availability

The data underpinning the analysis reported in this article are deposited in Zenodo at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15635303>.

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